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HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME – TOPIC HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05

*Wind energy in the natural and social environment
Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

wimby
WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

Grant Agreement No. 101083460

Starting date: 1st January 2023 – Duration: 36 months

**Deliverable D 3.3
Pilot region 3 – Styria (AT) report**

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable number	D3.3
Deliverable title	Pilot region Ennstal, Styria (AT) report
Work Package	WP3
Deliverable type	R
Dissemination level	P
Due date	31.10.2025 (Month 34)
Pages	66
Document version	3.0
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The WIMBY project has received funding from the European Union's research and innovation programme Horizon Europe under the grant agreement No. 101083460. This document reflects only the author's view, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

DOCUMENT CHANGE HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Description
DRAFT			
0.1	25.07.2025	Thomas Schauppenlehner, Eva Maria Konrad, Christian Mikovits (BOKU)	Creation
0.2	26.09.2025	Thomas Schauppenlehner, Eva Maria Konrad, Christian Mikovits (BOKU)	Consolidation of input from contributors
FIRST PEER REVIEW			
1.0	21.10.2025	Jørn Stave (Multiconsult), Mariana Carvalho (APREN)	Proofreading and peer review
1.1	24.10.2025	Thomas Schauppenlehner, Eva Maria Konrad (BOKU)	Consolidation of input from reviewers
COORDINATOR APPROVAL			
2.0	31.10.2025	Luis Ramirez Camargo, (UU)	Coordinator review
2.1	31.10.2025	Thomas Schauppenlehner, Eva Maria Konrad (BOKU)	Consolidation of input from coordinator
2.2	31.10.2025	Stella Arapoglou (VUB)	Coordinator approval
FINAL VERSION			
3.0	31.10.2025	Stella Arapoglou (VUB)	Format review, version ready for submission

SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This deliverable outlines stakeholder engagement methods and tools used in the Ennstal (Styria, Austria) pilot region workshops (21-24 October 2024), where participants explored wind farm scenario planning through 3D visualisations and a planning game. Additional research included a multi-criteria satisfaction analysis (MUSA) survey, semi-structured interviews, and mental models.

The outcomes and positive feedback from the workshops suggest that utilising a variety of collaborative approaches enhances the potential for participation in renewable energy projects.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AMA	AgrarMarkt Austria
BEV	Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying
BFW	Austrian Research Centre for Forests
DCM	Digital Cadastral Map
DOP	Digital Orthophoto
DSM	Digital Surface Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Aiding
MUSA	Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis
nDSM	Normalized Digital Surface Model
NEWA	New European Windatlas
OGD	Open Government Data
OSM	Open Street Map
SPSS	Statistical Product and Service Solutions
UNEP	UN Environment Programme
VGI	Volunteered Geographic Information
VR	Virtual Reality
WCMC	World Conservation Monitoring Centre

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the results of the workshops and collaborative actions conducted in the Ennstal pilot region in Styria from 21–24 October 2024, engaging adults and pupils to explore sustainable wind energy development at regional level. As a typical mountainous region, the pilot site represents a broad range of comparable regions in Europe, with a high-valued landscape scenery, ecologically important areas, high relief energy, and a significant economic reliance on tourism including landscape-related touristic infrastructures.

A core action was the interactive experience of scenario wind farm planning using immersive 3D visualisations and a planning game approach (see also Deliverable D5.3), which aimed to balance renewable energy goals with environmental conservation and tourism needs, aligning with Austria's 2030 and 2040 wind energy targets. To assess the impact of wind farms on biodiversity, habitat suitability maps were embedded (see Deliverable D1.8). During the action days on site, further research activities and interventions took place. These included a multi-criteria satisfaction analysis (MUSA) survey, interviews on project ramifications and acceptance, and a mental model study. In the end, 116 people with varied backgrounds and energy knowledge took part in one or more activities in the Ennstal. The findings from the workshops, surveys, and interviews highlight the complex interplay of opportunities and challenges associated with wind energy development in the region. While there is a foundation of support for renewable energy, significant concerns persist regarding environmental impacts, visual and spatial effects, and the preservation of the region's scenic landscape and tourism value. All objectives (wind power communication; WIMBY interactive map validation/improvement; immersive 3D platform validation/improvement; MCSA enhancement/validation) were fulfilled in accordance with the proposal. Furthermore, interviews and a mental model approach were applied in the pilot site regions

Note to readers: This report is part of a series of four pilot studies conducted as part of the WIMBY project. Each report focuses on the respective regional results. However, to ensure the readability of each individual report, there is some minor overlap in content (e.g. process descriptions, methods).

1 Introduction

1.1 Case Study Description

The pilot site Ennstal is a mountainous alpine valley in the Austrian federal state of Styria. Styria has a high share of mountainous regions, ranging from 200 to almost 3,000 m above sea level, a high proportion of coniferous forests (> 55%) and alpine meadows (7%). It is in the transitional area between the Alpine and Pannonian climate zone and offers a diversity of wildlife habitats and associated species distribution patterns. The region has a variety of suitable locations for the installation of wind turbines, especially in higher altitude areas and in forests. Alpine regions in particular offer considerable wind energy potential, characterized by high and constant wind speeds. As of 2025, Styria operates 122 wind turbines with a total capacity of 324 MW (IG Windkraft, 2025), representing a significant component of Austria's renewable energy infrastructure. While the federal state's goal for 2030 is an installed capacity of 1000 MW, the current expansion rate will result in an installed capacity of only 400 MW (Industriellenvereinigung Steiermark & Energie Steiermark, 2024). Developers in Styria benefit from existing land use regulations (Sapro Wind¹), which offer greater planning security compared to other federal states.

¹ <https://www.verwaltung.steiermark.at/cms/ziel/154055485/DE/>

Figure 1: Overview of the Ennstal/Styria pilot region and its location in Austria (Source: Open Street Map, BEV, BFW; Cartography: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

Due to the dynamic characteristic of mountainous areas in the Alps, the Ennstal pilot site (see Figure 1 above) offers a microcosm that provides insights into the conditions, opportunities and limitations for wind power expansion in the Alpine and mountainous regions. Its representative nature stems from several key characteristics that mirror challenges and opportunities found throughout alpine Europe. The absence of existing wind energy infrastructure makes this area particularly valuable for baseline studies, as it provides an undisturbed landscape free from the visual, acoustic, and ecological impacts typically associated with wind turbine installations. These conditions allow for comprehensive assessment of potential renewable energy development without the complications of pre-existing installations. Geographically, the region encompasses the full spectrum of alpine terrain, creating a diverse topographical canvas that ranges from high-altitude glacial environments and snow-covered peaks to densely populated valley floors and regional industrial facilities. The large differences in altitude encompasses alpine meadows, forested slopes, and

agricultural zones, each presenting distinct environmental conditions and land-use patterns that are characteristic for mountainous regions.

Tourism is a cornerstone of the regional economy. In 2023, the district accounted for 38.9% of all tourists overnight stays in Styria. As well as being an important Styrian winter sports centre, the region also offers a wide range of tourist attractions in summer (WIBIS Steiermark, 2024). Therefore, the economic dependence on landscape aesthetics and environmental quality adds another layer of complexity to any potential wind energy development considerations, as the region must balance economic diversification opportunities with the preservation of the natural and cultural heritage that draws visitors from around the world.

Together, these factors create a representative alpine setting that encapsulates the multifaceted challenges of sustainable development in mountain environments, as the implementation of wind energy projects depends largely on the local acceptance and the early involvement of stakeholders.

1.2 Objective

The workshop objective centres on engaging stakeholders to explore sustainable wind energy development in the Ennstal region, while balancing renewable energy goals with tourism and environmental conservation needs.

To facilitate collaborative stakeholder engagement in assessing the potential for wind energy development in the valley, leveraging the regions alpine environment as a representative case study for sustainable renewable energy planning across European mountain territories.

The specific objectives were:

- Analysing perception patterns and shifts: Evaluation of the shift from potential initial prejudices to more informed judgements after participants are provided with information and compromise scenarios through a serious game.
- Mapping spatial variations in perception: understanding how opinions and concerns differ across distinct communities and landscapes, correlating them with local specificities.

- Assessing stakeholder awareness: gauging the baseline level of knowledge among different groups regarding the technical, economic, and environmental implications of wind energy.
- Collecting qualitative feedback: gathering actionable insights, concerns, and "takeaways" directly from residents to inform more inclusive and effective development strategies.

The regional targets for the workshops are in line with Austria's target for 2030 to increase electricity generation from wind energy by 11 TWh per year (from 2020) and Styria's target for 2030 to achieve an installed wind power capacity of 1000 MW with an expected electricity generation of 2.9 TWh per year (Industriellenvereinigung Steiermark & Energie Steiermark, 2024). To achieve complete decarbonisation of the energy system in line with Austria's targets for 2040, an additional 26 TWh per year will be required compared to the reference year 2020 (Schmidt et al., 2021).

Based on the national strategy above, we downscaled these goals for the pilot site region. Therefore, we calculated the wind power potential for Austria at district level, based on potential locations (suitable land use, distance to houses and slope constraints), wind speeds and wind quality/capacity (NEWA²). In line with these potentials at district level, the possible contributions were scaled to the case study region. For the pilot region Ennstal we estimated a share of 0,6–0,7% from the federal goals, translating to 65–75 GWh per year for 2030, and 160–185 GWh per year for 2040. This means that, depending on site conditions, 8 to 12 turbines (with 3 to 3.5 MW each) are required to achieve the 2030 target, and 20 to 30 turbines to achieve the 2040 targets.

² New European Wind Atlas: <https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu/>

2 Material and Methods

2.1 Participant engagement

BOKU University takes the lead in this pilot region, contacting the stakeholders as well as selecting and organizing the locations for the workshops. Considerable support was also provided by UU's network on side.

The first step in the stakeholder engagement process was to compile a comprehensive list of all the potential stakeholders (see Section 6.3) for the workshops in Ennstal, Styria. This list included representatives from politics, nature conservation, tourism, and special interest groups such as the Chamber of Agriculture and IG Windkraft (representation group of interests in wind energy), as well as various regional associations and companies in the energy sector. Suitable schools for a student workshop were also identified.

Once the workshop locations had been selected, the affected communities were contacted by email and telephone to inform them about the planned workshops and arrange suitable venues. Subsequently, all potential stakeholders were emailed to share details about the workshops and invite them to participate. An information flyer containing details of the workshops and a QR code for easy registration was created and distributed (e.g. in hotels and town halls). In addition to email and telephone contact, professional and personal networks were utilized, alongside public information campaigns involving the communities, such as displaying information flyers and notices on websites, to recruit workshop participants.

2.2 Locations

The uniqueness of this pilot site lay in the challenge of addressing an entire region with both a high potential for wind power deployment and significant scenic and touristic value. To make the workshops more accessible to interested people across the valley, the workshops took place in two different locations. The municipalities of Irdning-Donnersbachtal and Michaelerberg-Pruggern were selected due to their central location and the availability of suitable venues for the workshops.

In Irdning, two workshops for adults were conducted in the town hall. Located at the foot of the Grimming mountain and at the entrance to the

Donnersbach valley, Irdning is a popular holiday destination offering activities for both culture and sports enthusiasts. In Michaelerberg-Pruggern, a workshop for adults was held in the seminar room at Thannegg Castle. Michaelerberg-Pruggern, situated west of Irdning and near the Sölktaier Nature Park, also provides a wide range of opportunities for winter and summer tourism.

To conduct workshops with pupils, two schools in the region were visited: BRG Stainach and HBLFA Raumberg-Gumpenstein.

2.3 Pilot site activities

The activities at the pilot sites included the following (see Figure 2):

- **Immersive 3D planning game:** an interactive scenario planning tool with immersive 3D visualisation designed to engage people and promote discussion about trade-offs, fears and expectations regarding wind power development
- **MUSA (Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis) Survey:** a structured survey to quantify how residents evaluate the entire range of wind farm impacts
- **Mental Models:** a method used to explore perceptions and understanding of the impacts of wind energy
- **Surveys and semi-structured interviews:** focused on project ramifications and acceptance
- **Other activities:** supplementary stakeholder engagement efforts aimed at collecting qualitative feedback on the WIMBY interactive map and forum (see Deliverable D5.1: Bakelants et al., 2024), and broader insights into the projects overall approach and methodology

Figure 2: Outline of activities at pilot region Ennstal (Graphic: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

The immersive 3D planning game was tailored to each specific pilot site and, together with the mental models, conducted during workshops with participants. Individuals were approached in public spaces, such as streets or local hotspots, for the MUSA Survey and the interviews on project impacts and acceptance. In some cases, interviews were also conducted with workshop participants after the sessions concluded. Other activities included a brief presentation of the WIMBY interactive map and forum, as well as semi-structured video interviews with selected stakeholders.

2.4 Immersive 3D planning game

2.4.1 Workshop Design and Data Collection

The planning game workshops aimed to explore potential wind energy developments through an interactive experience using immersive 3D visualizations and a planning game approach. For this purpose, the BOKU team developed an immersive 3D platform comprising three interacting components (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Core components of the immersive 3D platform developed for the four pilot sites within the WIMBY project (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024)

Data processing utilised free, open-source, site-specific data (e.g. ODG, VGI data, see Table 1), which was enhanced through manual and semi-automatic optimisations and provided the foundation for the game board, the game logic, and the development of immersive 3D environment.

The serious game approach relied on three types of visual output:

- The **game table output**, which served as a playing area for creating wind energy scenarios and working with maps during the workshops, using simple game bricks as input device;
- The **projector output**, to present a dashboard with 3D visuals, key data and environmental details; and
- The **immersive VR output**, which allowed users to explore realistic visualisations of their envisaged wind energy scenarios using VR glasses.

For more information on the immersive 3D platform, see Deliverable D5.3 (Schauppenlehner et al., 2024).

The workshops in the case study regions were divided into five stages:

1. **Welcoming and introduction**, with a briefing on the objectives and procedure of the workshop
2. **Baseline survey**
3. **Planning game and interaction with the 3D visualization**, where participants engaged with the platform
4. **Interactive discussions and summary of the workshop**, to reflect on outcomes and insights
5. **Debrief/feedback survey**

Data collection during the workshop focused on participant engagement, learning outcomes, and decision-making. A baseline survey assessed participants' knowledge, attitudes toward wind energy, and prior experience with participatory processes. A debrief and feedback survey at the end evaluated the 3D game's usability, learning impact, the immersive experience, and the overall process.

The immersive 3D planning game consists of two game phases, whereas game phase 1 addresses the identification of inclusion and exclusion zones and game phase 2 focuses on the virtually planning of windfarms to achieve given regional targets.

During the planning game, participants' statements, reasoning, questions, and concerns regarding game decisions were documented, with time stamps added to link them to specific game actions. Separate notes were also taken to record general observations of group dynamics and interactions during the game.

2.4.2 Geospatial data sources

Our immersive 3D workshop environment depends on high-quality datasets for accurate and close-to-reality visualizations. The table below summarizes all datasets used and processed to build the visuals and convey supplementary information.

Austrian public authorities offer a wide coverage of high-resolution open government data (OGD) including data for topography and landcover. They can be accessed via various national data portals and are freely available for download. Infrastructural data (buildings, roads, powerlines, man-made structures, etc.) is based on volunteered geographic information from Open Street Map as they exhibit high coverage and contain detailed spatial data on the above-mentioned categories in Austria.

Table 1: Datasets used for creating the 3D environment and game logic for the Ennstal/Styria pilot region

Category	Dataset	Source	Licence	URI/comment
True Colour Composite	Digital Orthophoto (DOP)	Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying (BEV)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://www.bev.gv.at/Services/Produkte/Luftbildprodukte/Orthophoto-Farbe.html
Topography	Digital Surface Model (DSM)	Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying (BEV)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://doi.org/10.48677/d8440772-79d8-45ff-92ab-892a68ebe589
	Digital Terrain Model (DTM)	Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying (BEV)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://doi.org/10.48677/5ce253fc-b7c5-4362-97af-6556c18a45d9
	Normalized Digital Surface Model (nDSM)	Derivate of [DSM, DTM]	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
Administrative	Digital Cadastral Map (DCM)	Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying	CC BY 4.0 AT	https://doi.org/10.48677/de5ff1da-9733-4fdd-ab49-88cfd5174c86
	Administrative Borders	OSM	ODbL	https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Tag%3aboundary=administrative
Land Cover	Sentinel-II Landcover	Umwelt-bundesamt GmbH	CC BY 4.0 International	https://www.data.gv.at/datasets/97327f91-93b7-4dbb-94a4-008a09f45d77?locale=en
	INVEKOS/IACS Agricultural Fields	AgrarMarkt Austria (AMA)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://www.data.gv.at/datasets/d09ee341-ed3a-4e48-bb7d-73c7861cb94c?locale=de
	Austrian Forest Map (Waldkarte)	Austrian Research Centre for Forests (BFW)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://data.inspire.gv.at/b87c2f56-ecd5-4703-baa3-8398e138a58c
	Small Woody Features	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service	CC BY 4.0 International	https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/high-resolution-layers/small-woody-features/small-woody-features-2015?tab=download
Infrastructure	Wind turbines	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Power lines	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Fences, Hedges	Derivate of [DOP, nDSM, DCM]	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
	Extra Objects	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Building Footprints	OSM	ODbL	https://www.openstreetmap.org
	Roads	OSM	ODbL	https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Key:highway
Energy	Wind Capacity Factor	New European Windatlas (NEWA)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu

	Wind Speeds	New European Windatlas (NEWA)	CC BY 4.0 International	https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu
	Potential for Wind Turbine Locations	Derivate of [DTM, Infrastructure, Wind Speeds]	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished
Environmental and Biological	World Database on Protected areas (2024)	IUCN and UNEP-WCMC	Non-Commercial use	https://www.protectedplanet.net
	Habitat suitability for grouse, woodpecker, dove and bats	Vishesh, L., Kunz, F., Nopp-Mayr, U., Schöll E.	Restricted	Created for internal use only, unpublished

2.4.3 Ecological data

To visualize the effects of wind farms on biodiversity, habitat suitability maps for nine threatened animal species were prepared. Habitat suitability maps predict the likelihood of a species occurring in an area, based on environmental variables, such as land cover, topography, and climate (Hirzel et al., 2006). Areas deemed suitable meet the ecological needs (e.g. breeding, foraging) of the specific species. However, while habitats may be suitable for a species, it does not automatically mean that the species will be present (Hirzel & Le Lay, 2008), because other factors, such as competition with other species (Jones et al., 2016) or more recent human disturbances in the habitat (Plante et al., 2018) might deter wildlife from using the specific sites. The method used for modeling habitat suitability is explained in detail in the deliverable D1.8 (Diengdoh et al., 2024).

The selected species are non-migratory, forest and woodland-dwelling species, because future wind farms in Styria are more likely to be developed in forested areas. Suitable habitat was visualized for three forest grouse species (western capercaillie (*Tetrao urogallus*), black grouse (*Lyrurus tetrix*), and hazel grouse (*Tetrastes bonasia*)), four woodpeckers (Syrian woodpecker (*Dendrocopos syriacus*), middle spotted woodpeckers (*Dendrocoptes medius*), lesser spotted woodpeckers (*Dryobates minor*), and grey-faced woodpeckers (*Picus canus*)), one pigeon (stock dove (*Columba oenas*)), and one bat species (lesser horseshoe bat (*Rhinolophus hipposideros*)). For each species group, a specific symbol was created. If the area selected for a wind farm deployment overlapped with at least one species from the respective group (grouse, woodpecker, pigeon, bat), the symbol was shown on the map. This approach ensured that stakeholders

were effectively informed about the potential effects of wind farms on biodiversity.

2.5 Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis (MUSA) framework

To capture a nuanced picture of how wind farms are affecting or will affect local communities, we designed a comprehensive satisfaction framework that runs in parallel with the stakeholder workshops. Its primary aim is to quantify how residents judge the full spectrum of wind-farm impacts, from noise, landscape change, and biodiversity concerns to local employment and community contribution. Because these dimensions often pull in different directions, analysing them one by one would hide critical trade-offs. Instead, we applied a multi-criteria setting that evaluates all aspects simultaneously.

The core of this setting is the Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis (MUSA), a well-established method within the wider family of Multi-Criteria Decision Aiding (MCDA). MUSA was originally created for customer-satisfaction studies in the service sector (Grigoroudis & Siskos, 2002). MUSA relies on preference disaggregation: Participants rate each criterion on a tailored Likert scale, with the number of categories and label wording adapted to the local context. The key requirement is that categories are strictly ordinal and consistently anchored so they can be mapped to MUSA's value functions. The algorithm infers criterion weights, partial value functions, and global satisfaction indices via ordinal regression. By deriving these parameters directly from response patterns, rather than asking analysts or respondents to assign weights manually, MUSA avoids the subjective bias common in many MCDA approaches.

Figure 4: Structure of a MUSA problem (Huang et al., 2024)

As illustrated in Figure 4, MUSA deconstructs global satisfaction into criterion-level components, showing how each attribute contributes to the overall score. This hierarchical view highlights both strengths and areas needing improvement, providing a transparent roadmap for raising public acceptance.

In practice, residents complete a survey that records both their overall satisfaction with nearby wind farms and their specific ratings on each criterion, using an ordered scale such as a five-point Likert range from “Extremely dissatisfied” to “Extremely satisfied.” These ordinal responses feed directly into MUSA, enabling us to quantify which attributes carry the greatest weight in shaping community sentiment.

We embed MUSA in our broader Multi-Criteria Satisfaction Analysis (MCSA) framework, which adds the practical guideline needed for field application (as shown in Figure 5). For detailed introduction of the MCSA framework, please refer to Deliverable D4.2 (Huang et al., 2024).

Figure 5: Satisfaction analysis workflow (Huang et al., 2024)

2.6 Mental Models

We investigated workshop participants' mental models of perceived wind energy impacts. Mental models explore individuals' cognitive representations of the external world, including perceptions of interrelations within a system and system components (Van Den Broek et al., 2025). To elicit these mental models, we apply a standardised mental model tool called M-Tool³, which allows participants to create their mental model by mapping relevant concepts, in our case, the perceived impacts of wind farms, and the directional relations as an influence diagram (Van Den Broek et al., 2021). We applied a two-step approach. In the first step, we compiled wind farm impacts from a literature review and from a survey with the target audience. In the survey participants were asked about the impacts of wind farms they could think of in all four pilot site countries to determine the most commonly perceived impacts. We analysed the open text responses where people described wind farm impacts following the guidelines on conducting

³ <https://m-tool.org/>

thematic analysis by Braun and Clarke (2023). We applied a deductive or “theory-driven” approach, where produced codes are predefined through a theoretically informed interpretation by the researcher, in this case based on the impacts reported in relevant literature (Byrne, 2022). A selection of 20 impacts was made, comprising the most mentioned social, ecological, economic and energy production-related impacts (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Selection of impacts and the target variable (wind farm) used for the mental model exercise (Graphic: Leanda Vedder)

In the second step, participants could use these impacts to create their mental model by connecting them with each other or the target variable, the wind farm in operation, with three weighted arrows, where the weight represents the strength of the influence between images (see Figure 7). Participants were handed tablets with headphones where they were first presented with an instruction video that explained the concepts and instructions of how to create their model, then they were prompted to create their mental model about impacts they expect or have experienced from wind farms. Afterwards, they filled in a short survey on their general attitude towards wind farms (on a scale from 0 = I fully oppose wind farms, to 100 = I fully support wind farms), their perspective on the energy transition and renewable energy policies. We applied a network analysis approach to analyse the data, where the impacts serve as nodes and the arrows represent the edges of the network. In this way, we investigate the most used

impacts, the most used direct connections between concepts and the most used indirect connections for each case study. This allows us to gain insights into participants' understanding of the system, especially the indirect connections provide us with an understanding of participants' capability to conceptualise complex interrelations and systems thinking.

Figure 7: M-Tool mapping screen with a mental model created by a participant.
(Graphic: Leanda Vedder)

The mental model exercise was implemented in conjunction with the 3D immersive environment during the workshops. To control for the potential influence of the 3D experience on participants' perceptions of wind farm impacts, efforts were made to achieve an even distribution of participants completing the mental model task either before or after engaging with the 3D environment. This allocation was determined based on the specific workshop arrangements in each pilot region. In Austria, participants were divided such that approximately half completed the mental model exercise before engaging with the 3D environment (N=18), while the other half did so afterwards (N=20). This split was influenced by the pace at which participants completed the baseline survey. A smaller group of participants (N=9) was recruited outside the workshop setting.

2.7 Interviews on Project Ramifications and Acceptance

The term NIMBY (Not in my Back Yard) is widely used to describe local opposition to nearby developments, particularly those involving energy infrastructure such as wind turbines or transmission lines (Devine-Wright, 2009). As Brennan and Van Rensburg (2016) argue, negative externalities associated with wind energy projects (e.g., noise or visual intrusions) can foster NIMBYism. These localised externalities manifest in several ways. A concise review of the literature identifies four primary drivers of local resistance: (i) the environmental impacts of wind energy projects; (ii) their technical and physical characteristics; (iii) the distribution of costs and benefits related to the project; and (iv) the behaviour and practices of project developers.

With respect to **environmental impacts**, research highlights several key concerns: noise emissions (Langer et al., 2016, 2017); perceived levels of infrasound (Langer et al., 2018); the visual prominence of wind turbines (Langer et al., 2016, 2017); and their setback distances (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016); shadow flicker (Devine-Wright, 2005; Jensen et al., 2014); impacts on biodiversity (Ladenburg & Dubgaard, 2009) and property values (Jensen et al., 2014); grid expansion associated with projects (Langer et al., 2018); and the broader regional distribution of turbines (Bidwell, 2013).

Regarding **physical characteristics**, studies primarily focus on turbine height and the number of turbines. Brennan and Van Rensburg (2016), using a discrete choice experiment, found that higher turbines require greater compensation payments to ensure local acceptance. They also observed that residents demand increased compensation for each additional turbine within a wind farm. Similarly, Langer et al. (2016) confirmed that the steady expansion of turbines in Bavaria, Germany, has intensified conflicts with local communities.

Research on the **distribution of costs and benefits** underscores the importance of perceived distributive justice (Ciupuliga & Cuppen, 2013; Huijts et al., 2012). Community benefits and financial participation have been shown to positively influence local acceptance (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Langer et al., 2017; Walter, 2014). Research suggests that community benefits are better apt to increase wind energy project acceptance than individual benefits (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Walker et al., 2014; Walter, 2014). However, many studies also detected cheaper electricity for locals as convincing

benefit (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016; Cass et al., 2010). It should be noted that some residents might perceive financial benefits as bribery (Cass et al., 2010; Macdonald et al., 2017).

Finally, the **behaviour of wind energy developers** plays a crucial role in acceptance. Studies highlight that perceived trustworthiness strongly influences public attitudes (Graham et al., 2009; Jobert et al., 2007). Trust can be fostered by enhancing procedural justice, particularly through transparent and high-quality information (Zoll & Ackermann, 2001). Citizen participation is equally significant, with residents represented by local community members showing greater support for projects (Brennan & Van Rensburg, 2016; Corscadden et al., 2012; Langer et al., 2017; McLaren Loring, 2007; Upham & García Perez, 2015).

Having the four aforementioned factors (i)–(iv) in mind, we addressed the following research question (RQ1): **Can certain project ramifications affect respondents' attitudes toward a wind energy project in the region and if so, to what extent?** To answer this, we gathered quantitative data through surveys and semi-structured interviews, assessing whether elements such as smaller turbine designs or financial compensation schemes influence local attitudes positively or negatively. By examining a variety of factors within one survey, this report provides a holistic review of their impact on local attitudes across different regions.

In a second step, we integrated these findings with respondents' general attitudes toward wind energy and their views on projects in their region. Research indicates that community benefits and financial participation schemes can positively influence local acceptance, particularly among residents already favourably inclined toward wind energy (Hyland & Bertsch, 2018; Langer et al., 2017; Walter, 2014). Building on this assumption, we explored a second research question (RQ2): **Do project ramifications also affect the attitudes of respondents who are negatively inclined towards the project in the region?** This question directly follows from RQ1.

To analyse respondents' attitudes, we structured the questionnaire into three parts addressing their general attitude towards wind energy (Part I), their concrete attitude towards a wind energy project in the region, regardless of specific project characteristics (Part II), and their concrete attitude towards a wind energy project in the region, with defined project characteristics (Part III). This approach follows Walter (2014), who

differentiates between public attitude toward wind energy (general perceptions at the national level), attitude toward local wind energy projects (views on projects in one’s vicinity irrespective of specific features), and local acceptance of wind energy projects (opinions on a specific project, considering its characteristics). A complete list of the questions posed in Parts I–III is provided in Annex I with additional details on the design process available in WIMBY Deliverable 4.4 (Lowitzsch et al., 2024). Figure 8 provides a visualisation of the methodology.

Figure 8: Overview of methodological approach (Elaboration: Monika Bucha)

2.8 Other activities

Each workshop envisioned additional stakeholder engagement activities, planned to collect qualitative feedback on the WIMBY interactive map, the forum and any further insight about the overall project approach and methodology. Such activities were organised as follows:

- A short interactive presentation of the WIMBY interactive map and forum including a real-time simulation
- Semi-structured interviews to selected stakeholders

The interactive presentation of the Map and Forum: For the workshops with adults in Styria the WIMBY interactive map and forum was used and presented in two different forms. The first one was as supporting material for the stakeholders during the 3D Game. Participants were interested in having

detailed wind speed and energy density data, i.e. the data exploration capabilities of the tool, before making their decisions about locations to deploy wind power. The UU team was navigating the participants through the layers and locations for which they wanted to have the data during the game. That interaction with the participants also opened the door for a more detailed presentation of the WIMBY interactive map after the 3D game and its debriefing was completed. The UU team presented the rest of the capabilities of the WIMBY interactive map putting in this case emphasis on the wind farm simulation module. Participants and especially the ones more related to the wind power industry engaged in a constructive conversation about the capabilities of the map, its potential to be used in their regular activities and feedback for the assessment modules that had been implemented until that moment.

Semi-structured video interviews with selected stakeholders were conducted with a twofold objective: (i) to gather opinions and perspectives on wind energy and the local context that could enrich quantitative survey results with qualitative insights, and (ii) to ensure that local voices were heard and shared at the community level, fostering participation and exchange of views. To maximise visibility, once published, all links to the interviews were circulated among the relevant organisations and interviewees, and promoted through all WIMBY communication channels, always with prior consent.

The following activities took place to conduct the interviews:

- Prepared a standard list of guiding questions (see Section 6.2), common to all pilot sites. (Note: The questions were designed to guide the conversation and ensure key themes were addressed. However, the interviews remained flexible: depending on the background of the interviewee, their specific role or expertise, and the dynamics of the workshop, questions were adapted or reformulated on the spot to capture the most relevant insights and perspectives.)
- Identified potential candidates in advance by liaising with pilot site leaders.
- Collected signed consent forms from interviewees, authorising both the recording and the publication of the videos on WIMBY communication channels
- Planned 20-minute video-recording sessions.

Thanks to the informal setting and the open-ended questions, interviewees had the space to express their views freely. This allowed the team to capture local nuances and perceptions of wind energy projects and renewable energy systems more broadly. After recording, a preliminary edited version was shared with participants and pilot site leaders for approval prior to publication. Highlights and key takeaways from the interviews are presented in Section 3.5.

3 Results and Discussion

From 21st to 24th October 2024, a total of 25 adults and 18 pupils from the Ennstal region in Styria took part in the interactive workshops. Three workshops were organised for adults, two in Irdning and one in Michaelerberg. One workshop was organised for pupils at each of two different schools: BRG Stainach and HBLFA Raumberg-Gumpenstein.

3.1 Immersive 3D planning game

This chapter presents the results of the two game phases, the analysis of the baseline survey and the workshop evaluation.

3.1.1 Game phase 1: Go and No-Go zones for Windfarm development

The discussion was very broad in most workshops, but it was often characterized by fears and concerns about the impact of wind farms on the landscape, personal living environments and tourism. As a result (see Figure 9), No-Go zones were mainly designated in populated valley areas (region 4 and 5) and in regions that are attractive for tourism value creation (which often overlap with ecologically valuable zones in this region) (region 7 and 8). As Go zones, skiing infrastructure (region 1, 9 and 10) and regions with a higher share of industry were mostly mentioned (region 2 and 6).

Figure 9: Distribution and density of Go and No-Go zones (Source: Open Street Map, BEV, BFW, WIMBY; Cartography: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

This classification process was accompanied by a discussion of the reasons behind it. The main arguments are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Key arguments (Pros and Cons) for the considered regions in the Ennstal/Styria pilot site

No.	Pros and Cons
1	Tauplitz: Existing small ski infrastructure but low local energy demand
2	Liezen (local capital): Unattractive industrial area and high local energy demand (industry, housing)
3	Viebergalm/Gröbming: Local energy demand from a nearby cement factory
4	Main valley: Too close to villages, a military airport and attractive valley

5	Mitterberg: Central hill as a landmark for wind energy; close to settlements and poor wind conditions
6	Zwölferkogel: Mountain range with good wind conditions and close to the consumers
7	Sölkttäler: Nature Park with attractive natural landscapes
8	Stoderzinken: Remarkable Mountain peak and high visibility from the valley
9	Planneralm: Existing small ski infrastructure but low local energy demand
10	Schladming: Large skiing resort with lots of infrastructure and consumers

3.1.2 Game phase 2: Virtual Windfarm development

The aim of game phase 2 was to develop specific wind farms based on the previously identified Go zones. By placing individual wind turbines or entire wind farms on the interactive game board, the effects on the landscape can be experienced in real time in the 3D environment. In addition, indicators provide information about the effects on ecological factors at the selected location and the contribution of the wind turbines to the game objectives explained in chapter 1.2 (based on turbine sizes and local wind conditions). With the help of VR glasses, immersive visualizations are also possible to better perceive realistic perspectives and proportions. Below, three different wind farm scenarios that were developed during the workshops are explained using fact sheets.

Scenario 1: “Not in my backyard”

According to the Go zones from game phase 1, most participants wanted to move the windfarm far away from the densely populated Ennstal with towns, villages and settlements. One idea was to move it to a cement industry facility in the village of Gröbming (see Figure 10). The Viehbergalm in the north of Gröbming is hardly visible from the valley itself, but wind conditions are not that good (due to a slight basin location) and the turbines are visible from the mountain tops of Stoderzinken and Grimming (viewpoint 2 and 3), which are also of interest to tourists. Furthermore, due to the remote region, there might be an impact on suitable habitats for grouse and woodpecker.

Viehbergalm

Remote alpine pasture in the mountainous north region

5 wind turbines
Capacity: 3,5 MW

Figure 10: Factsheet Scenario 1: “Not in my backyard” (Source: BEV, BFW, Open Street Map, WIMBY; Cartography and Layout: Thomas Schauppenlehner)

Scenario 2: “Synergies with touristic infrastructure”

In a second virtual windfarm scenario, a focus was set to skiing resorts of which there are several in the region. The Planneralm (see Figure 11) is a small skiing resort in the southeast of the valley and there are some suitable locations directly in the skiing area. The wind conditions are better compared to Viehbergalm and the visual impacts seem low due to the embedment into the existing cable car and lift infrastructure. Because of vast forests, the windfarm is also difficult to see from the surrounding area. However, locals reported that there are some small low-wind basins that do not appear on the wind map, and it is also unclear how much energy the skiing resorts really need and what to do with the energy in the summer season.

Planneralm

Skiing resort

4 wind turbines
Capacity: 3,5 MW

Figure 11: Factsheet Scenario 2: “Synergies with touristic infrastructure” (Source: BEV, BFW, Open Street Map, WIMBY; Cartography and Layout: Thomas Schuppenlehner)

Scenario 3: “Serving the valley”

In a third scenario a mountain ridge in the southwest of the villages was used to place 5 turbines in a row (see Figure 12). Due to the good wind conditions there, these 5 turbines (with 3,5 MW each) are almost enough to reach the 2030 goal for transforming the entire regional electricity demand to renewable energy. Compared to the other two scenarios, they are more visible also from attractive locations such as the touristic village of Pürgg

(viewpoint 3) or the Castle of Trautenfels (viewpoint 4). Due to the distance between 6,5 and 8 km from the main valley with settlements, they appear very small and fuzzy because of the usual atmospheric haze (viewpoint 2).

Figure 12: Factsheet Scenario 2: “Serving the valley” (Source: BEV, BFW, Open Street Map, WIMBY; Cartography and Layout: Thomas Schuppenlehner)

In summary, it became clear that the 2050 targets seem difficult to achieve in this region due to spatial and visual concerns. The landscape and tourist value are seen as particularly important. There were also some voices in favour of highly visible wind turbines in the centre of the valley (Mitterberg)

as a sign of sustainability. However, the required distance conditions from residential buildings were not met here. In the peripheral areas of the pilot region, there were other areas that could be suitable, such as the very large Schladming ski resort and the industrial zone around Liezen. However, these were not part of the predefined study area.

3.1.3 Analysis of questionnaires

The collected questionnaires were entered into an Excel spreadsheet and analysed using SPSS. The following section summarises the results of the baseline survey of adults, the baseline survey of pupils and the results of the debrief questionnaires completed by both groups.

Baseline Survey Adults

The average age of workshop participants was 49, with the oldest person being 75 and the youngest 25. Of those surveyed, 60.9% were men and 39.1% were women, with 62.5% of all respondents living in the Ennstal valley. Two-thirds had a higher education qualification, and many had professional experience with renewable energy development (44%). To find out more about renewable energy, 79% primarily use the internet or social media.

More than half (52.2%) support the expansion of wind energy (see Figure 13a), but only 12.5% consider it the most important renewable energy source. While 58.3% believe wind energy could contribute to a sustainable regional energy supply, only 20.8% think it could effectively cover their entire energy needs (see Figure 14c). Many (58.4%) do not feel sufficiently involved in decisions about wind power projects (see Figure 13b) and only 28% believe that incentives and opportunities for expanding wind energy in Austria are sufficient. At the same time, interest in actively participating in relevant initiatives was rather low and only 12.5% expressed general concerns about wind turbines in the region.

Figure 13: a) Do you generally support the expansion of wind energy? (n=23) b) Do you feel involved in the decision-making processes related to wind energy projects in your region? (n=24) c) How do you rate the level of public support for wind energy projects in Ennstal? (n=25)

Opinions on the impact of wind power on the environment and the economy are divided. While 48% see positive effects on the local environment and regional economy, 40% expressed concerns about social and ecological consequences. In particular, 48% rated the impact on biodiversity and the landscape as high (see Figure 14a). For 72% of the respondents, it is very important that environmental impact assessments and mitigation measures be carried out for wind energy projects (see Figure 14b). Research is also important from the participant's point of view: 91.7% see a need for research, particularly on reducing the impact on wildlife, changing the landscape and integrating energy storage systems.

Figure 14: a) How do you assess the potential environmental impacts of wind power, particularly regarding biodiversity and landscape aesthetics? (n=25) b) How important is it to conduct environmental impact assessments and implement mitigation measures for wind energy projects? (n=25) c) In your opinion, how effectively could wind energy meet the energy demand in your region? (n=24)

Almost half of those surveyed (48%) consider public support for wind energy projects in the Ennstal to be low (see Figure 13c). Acceptance within their own community is viewed even more critically: 64% rate it as low. As a result, 48% of respondents believe that the involvement of various interest groups (associations, citizens' initiatives, etc.) is important for the success of wind energy projects, with a third willing to participate in such groups themselves. Politically, respondents would like to see two measures in particular: incentives for investment in renewable energy and simpler approval procedures.

Despite the challenges, respondents see the greatest advantages of wind energy in the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and lower energy costs. It is particularly important to them that the population has a say in location decisions to minimise the impact on the landscape, especially regarding the preservation of habitats and visual effects.

Baseline Survey Students

The students surveyed were between 15 and 17 years old, and more girls (55.6%) than boys (44.4%) participated in the workshops. All (100%) had already heard about renewable energy at school (see Figure 15a), especially in physics lessons, but only 22.2% felt well informed about wind power (see Figure 15b). Only half of the students had seen a wind farm up close, yet 78.6% would like to learn more about how wind energy works. The internet

and social media are the most important sources of information for 83.3%. Most only sometimes talk to friends or family about renewable energy.

More than 60% of the students surveyed consider wind energy to be important for the future of our energy supply (see Figure 16a) and support its expansion, at least to some extent (see Figure 16b). However, over 50% are concerned about the potential negative effects of wind farms on the environment and society (see Figure 16c). 44.4% also fear negative effects on the landscape, while 47.1% see lower energy costs as an advantage.

Figure 15: a) Have you already learned something about renewable energy in school or through other activities? (n=17) b) I believe that I am well informed about wind energy. (n=18)

Public support for wind energy projects is rated as moderate by 66.7% and acceptance is even lower with 50%. As a result, almost 90% believe it is important to involve the population in wind power projects. Over 40% believe that wind power is important for the energy transition, yet 30% of the students surveyed believe that there is no suitable location for wind turbines in their region.

Figure 16: a) Do you believe wind energy is important for our energy future? (n=18) b) Do you support the development of wind energy? (n=18) c) Are you concerned about potential social and environmental impacts of wind energy projects? (n=18)

Workshop Feedback

The response to the workshops was positive from both adults (see Figure 17a) and students. The interactive methods were well received, and participants found the graphic quality of the 3D visualisations appealing and realistic. Although 41.7% of the participating adults had no experience with computer games, many had already had experience with virtual reality (VR), mostly in a training or simulation context.

Over 40% of adult participants believed that the game helped them to better understand wind energy concepts and initiatives, while over 50% felt that it helped them to better assess the potential impact on their region (see Figure 17b). 44% stated that the workshop had influenced their attitude towards renewable energy, while 40% felt that their confidence in wind energy initiatives had been strengthened (see Figure 17c). A large proportion of participants (68%) would like to see more renewable energy initiatives and opportunities for participation in their community. Almost two-thirds (64%) would like to participate in similar events in future. 80% of participants also believe that the simulation game could be used to address other regional issues, such as spatial planning or photovoltaics. This shows that playful approaches can make an important contribution to educating and involving the population.

Figure 17: Feedback Adults a) Overall, the experience of participating in a wind energy game was positive (n=25) b) The game helped me to assess the potential impact on my region (n=25) c) Did the workshop increase your confidence in supporting wind energy initiatives? (n=25)

The participating students also showed a great deal of interest in the topic. Almost all of them (94.4%) enjoyed the educational game (see Figure 18a), and more than 70% said that the interactive role play helped them to develop a better understanding of wind energy projects (see Figure 18b). More than half of them found the 3D visualisations appealing and realistic. Two-thirds said that the workshop had changed their views on and knowledge of renewable energy (see Figure 18c), and 50% said that it had strengthened their confidence in supporting wind energy projects. Over 64% would like to see more renewable energy initiatives and opportunities for participation in their region, and more than 40% would like to take part in similar workshops or events in the future.

Figure 18: Feedback Students a) The role-play combined with a learning game was enjoyable and interesting. (n=18) b) The game helped me better understand wind energy concepts and initiatives, as well as their potential impact on my community. (n=18) c) Did the workshop influence your knowledge and perceptions of renewable energy? (n=18)

3.2 MUSA

This section summarises preliminary results from Styria; a full technical analysis appears in Deliverable D4.6 (in progress). All pilot sites employed the same set of evaluation criteria: three overarching dimensions: environmental, community, and individual. They are subdivided into 12 specific subcriteria (see Table 3). Each sub-criterion was measured on a scale suited to its nature: for instance, “Undesired land-use changes” used a four-point Likert scale, whereas “Reduction of greenhouse-gas emissions” was assessed on a five-point scale.

Table 3: Set of satisfaction criteria

Dimension (Criterion)	Sub-criterion
Environmental	Undesired land use changes
	Impact on biodiversity
	Reduce Greenhouse gas emissions (GHG)
Community	Economic impact on the community
	Negative effect on community lifestyle
	Safety risks to people and infrastructures
	Raise social awareness and political engagement
	Long term maintenance and decommissioning plans

Individual	Impact on personal finances
	Negative effect on the landscape's aesthetics
	Disturbance from noise pollution
	Disturbance from shadow flicker

In Styria, 44 residents completed the MCSA survey. Figure 19 shows the resulting satisfaction curves for each sub-criterion.

Figure 19: Subcriteria satisfaction functions of Styria responses

Every curve begins at a satisfaction value of 0 for the lowest response level and rises to 100 at the highest, allowing us to read exactly how much satisfaction a given response implies. Take the sub-criterion “Undesired land-use changes,” posed as: “Do you believe that the construction of wind turbines will lead to undesirable land-use changes?” Respondents chose from four options: “To a large extent” (level 1), “To a moderate extent” (level 2), “To a lesser extent” (level 3), and “Not at all” (level 4). A response of “To a

lesser extent” (level 3) maps to a satisfaction score of 76.1. It is well above the neutral 66.7 implied by a linear 4-point mapping (0, 33.3, 66.7, 100), which indicates considerable comfort with the potential impact. The curves also reveal how demanding respondents are. For “Negative effect on the landscape’s aesthetics,” the curve rises so quickly that every response except the most negative scores above 90, suggesting residents are broadly satisfied on this point. In fact, all sub-criteria display similarly steep satisfaction curves, indicating that Styrian participants have low required improvement (i.e., modest performance thresholds) and are therefore readily satisfied. It should be noted that the MUSA questionnaire showed respondents a photograph of a single wind turbine on the Sommeralm (north of Graz) and asked them to rate their current satisfaction. Onshore deployment in Styria is presently limited. Accordingly, the high landscape scores reflect satisfaction under the current low-visibility status quo.

3.3 Mental Models

In Styria, participants (N = 47) constructed mental models using an average of 11.95 concepts (SD = 4.47) and connected them with a mean of 14.02 arrows (SD = 7.35). While a broad spectrum of impacts was included, there was a notable emphasis on environmental concerns (see Figure 20). The most frequently used concepts were Biodiversity Loss, CO₂ Reduction, and Visual Landscape Change. The most common direct connection was to Sustainable Energy, followed by links to Visual Landscape Change and Wildlife Disruption. In terms of indirect connections, the most prevalent was from Wildlife Disruption to Biodiversity Loss, followed by connections between CO₂ Reduction and Climate Change, and between Sustainable Energy and CO₂ Reduction. Participants in Styria expressed a relatively high level of support for wind energy, with a mean score of 71.87 (SD = 19.73). Despite this overall support, participants demonstrated considerable awareness of potential environmental impacts. The heightened sensitivity to environmental issues may be attributed to the region’s strong identification with its scenic landscape and the importance of tourism, which could contribute to increased concern over the ecological effects of wind energy development.

Figure 20: Aggregated mental model of wind farm impacts among participants from Styria. The thickness of the arrows represents the total weight of the connections across individual mental models, with thicker arrows indicating stronger connections. Note: Only connections with an above-average aggregated weight are shown (Source: Mental model data, Graphic: Leanda Vedder)

3.4 Interviews on Project Ramifications and Acceptance

In total, 25 interviews were conducted (28% female, 72% male) both during workshops (see Section 2.3) and in public spaces such as streets, churches, and municipal buildings. Two interviews were conducted online via MS Teams with cameras on. Some participants were contacted in advance via email and via phone to arrange a meeting, and interviews lasted between 15 - 60 minutes.

These provided a small snapshot of local attitudes toward wind energy projects. Based on question (in the following: Q) 1–8 (see Section 6.1), only one respondent opposed wind energy, 14 were neutral, and ten were supportive (see Figure 21a). When asked directly about their feelings toward the construction of a hypothetical wind energy project in their vicinity (Q11), **five respondents expressed negative or very negative feelings** (see pie to the left in Figure 21b). Interestingly, almost all of them still considered project participation to be important or very important (Q12; see Figure 21b, right

pie). This suggests that even individuals initially opposed to such projects may become more accepting if provided with meaningful opportunities for participation. This hypothesis is examined further in the following paragraphs.

In the following, we will also focus on the impact of project adaptations on those that have expressed very negative, negative or neutral feelings towards a potential wind energy project in their region (n = 14). In the following, we refer to this group of respondents as sceptics.

Figure 21: a) General attitude towards wind energy (n = 25) b) Feelings towards wind energy projects & the importance to participate (n = 25)

The analysis of **Q13** (*Which of the following technical changes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?*; see Section 6.1) revealed that 17 respondents supported altering turbine height, nine supported changes to setback distances, eight supported altering the number of turbines and seven supported technical measures to avoid bird strikes (see Figure 22, left pies). In other words, our study shows that up to 68% of respondents indicated increased support when technical adaptations addressed either (i) environmental impacts or (ii) the physical characteristics of wind energy projects (see Section 6.1).

Up to 78% of the respondents who indicated increased support towards a wind energy project in their region when technical adaptations were sceptics. This suggests that while some measures primarily strengthen

support among those already convinced, certain adaptations can also influence sceptical respondents. Among the four technical measures in Q13, changing the turbine height was the most effective, with 79% of sceptics indicating increased acceptance, followed by altering the setback distance (50%), reducing the number of turbines (36%), and offering technical measures to avoid bird strikes (28%) (see Figure 22, right pies).

Figure 22: Technical changes which would increase one’s willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 25)

Q14 (Which of the following financial participation mechanisms would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?; see Section 6.1) showed that financial participation was indeed appealing to certain respondents: twelve supported discounted electricity, ten preferred acquiring shares with personal funds, another ten supported financial participation for their municipality, and two supported acquiring shares through external financing (see Figure 23, left pies). In total, up to 48% of respondents were more willing to support a project when offered financial participation schemes; this directly addresses (iii) the distribution of ills and benefits (see Section 6.1).

Up to 57% of the respondents who indicated increased support towards a wind energy project in their region when financial participation were sceptics. Again, while some mechanisms appeal mainly to supporters, others also appeal to sceptics: Financial participation of the municipality proved most effective (57%), followed by the possibility to acquire project shares with foreign money (50%), the possibility to acquire project shares with own money (40%) and discounted electricity (17%) (see Figure 23, right pies).

Figure 23: Financial participation mechanisms which would increase one's willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 25)

For **Q15** (*Which of the following options for engagement in the decision-making processes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?*; see Section 6.1), 20 respondents supported early involvement, 13 favoured involvements in project implementation, another 13 favoured having a municipal representative on the board of directors and eleven preferred regular written updates (see Figure 24, left pies). Overall, up to 80% of respondents showed increased willingness to support a project when given opportunities for active engagement in decision-making,

indirectly depending on (iv) the behaviour of wind energy project developers (see Section 6.1).

Up to 86% of the respondents who indicated increased support towards a wind energy project in their region when early engagement was offered were sceptics. Among the four measures, the most appealing one for sceptics is offering participation in project implementation (86%), followed by granting an elected municipal representative a seat on the project's board of directors (71%), early involvement in the project planning and siting processes (57%), and regular written updates (29%) (see Figure 24 , right pies).

Figure 24: Options for engagement in the decision-making processes which would increase one's willingness to support regional wind energy projects (n = 25)

3.5 Other Activities

Presentation of the WIMBY interactive map and forum

The WIMBY interactive map exploratory layers proved to be very useful to acquire information about the availability of wind resources. Participants of the 3D game in many cases based their locational choices for wind farms on the information that they obtained from the WIMBY interactive map. This

also motivated the integration of this underlying data directly in the 3D game for the pilot site workshops that took place after this one.

Some of the interactions with stakeholders around the WIMBY interactive map went into a lot of detail which led to suggestions for improvement of the information panels and the presentation of the model results. This led to e.g., the development of information panels that can be contracted while exploring the results of the simulation. Moreover, for the specific case of the noise and shadow flicker models a general simplification of the results presentation was requested. This feedback has contributed to the decisions that were made about the way to present the results of the final versions of these models. Instead of presenting continuous information now we have clustered results to values and thresholds that are relevant for decision making.

In general, we got positive feedback about the added value of such a tool and the willingness to use it once it becomes publicly available. For some participants we have shared the link for early testing.

Video interviews

In Styria, three video interviews were collected, plus one additional interview to the pilot site leader BOKU. All interviews can be found on the WIMBY YouTube playlist⁴. The highlights and key messages are summarised in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Summary of stakeholder interviews

Styria	Former wind energy worker from the USA	“Wind power can generate clean energy without disrupting life as much as fossil fuels do. Of course, nobody wants turbines blocking the view of the Alps, but once they’re up, farming and grazing can continue around them. The real choice is whether we prefer a few turbines in windy spots, or coal and oil changing the climate.”
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⁴ <https://youtube.com/playlist?list=PLna5U7-OPgOtnOyUQbQhSDyjtFc8yE--p&si=vED0egy6ddPwIVa3>

Styria	Researcher	“From monks to hunters, local officials to environmentalists – we spoke with so many different voices here in Styria. Each had their own hopes, worries, and expectations. What stood out is that acceptance grows when people are heard and when the energy transition is shaped together.”
Styria	Tourist from Vienna	“Wind projects may raise concerns about noise, wildlife, or the view, but with creativity and community involvement, acceptance can grow. Imagine local companies taking part in construction, or turbines hosting climbing parks and cultural events. It’s about making wind energy a shared opportunity, not just infrastructure.”
Christian Mikovits	Styria onshore pilot site leader and researcher at BOKU University	“In Austria, our pilot site is in a challenging Alpine area, densely populated valleys, forests, protected habitats, even a Nature Park nearby. It’s not the easiest place to plan wind projects, but that’s exactly why we chose it. With WIMBY’s 3D planning platform, we engage stakeholders directly, residents, political decision-makers, farmers, even school classes. Instead of showing fixed plans, we let them ‘play the planning game’ themselves, seeing in realistic ways how turbines could fit (or not) into their landscape. It forces everyone to face the trade-offs and understand how projects are developed, from the bottom up.”

Figure 25: Video snapshots from the interviews

4 Conclusion and recommendations

The activities in the Ennstal revealed significant concerns about the spatial and visual impacts of wind farms, particularly regarding their effects on the landscape, personal living environments, and tourism. These concerns led to designation of No-Go zones in populated valleys and regions with high tourism value, which often coincide with ecologically sensitive zones. Conversely, Go zones were identified in regions with existing skiing infrastructure and a higher concentration of industry. While some participants supported the idea of visible wind turbines as symbols of sustainability, practical constraints, such as the required distances from residential areas, limited their feasibility. Areas such as the Schladming ski resort and an industrial area near the regional capital Liezen have been identified as potentially suitable for wind energy projects, but these areas are located on the outer edge of the pilot area. Considering these spatial, visual and ecological concerns will be critical for advancing wind energy development in the scenic and touristic regions like the Ennstal.

The findings of the surveys highlight both opportunities and challenges for wind energy projects in the Ennstal. While adults and students generally support renewable energy, concerns about environmental and social impacts, as well as limited public involvement in decision-making, remain significant barriers to broader acceptance. Nevertheless, across all pilot sites, the MCSA survey in the Ennstal shows the highest satisfaction with the visual impact of wind turbines. A plausible explanation is that wind deployment there is currently limited; since the MUSA survey measures current satisfaction with existing turbines, respondents report low perceived visual intrusion

However, their mental models also reveal a strong sensitivity to ecological issues, such as biodiversity loss and visual landscape changes, reflecting the region's reliance on its scenic landscape and tourism. Despite these concerns, there is broad recognition of the sustainability and climate change mitigation benefits of wind energy. Interviews suggest that local acceptance can be improved through measures such as adjusting turbine height, reducing the number of turbines, increasing setback distances, and ensuring early public involvement in planning and implementation.

The workshops demonstrated the value of interactive and educational approaches, such as 3D visualisations and simulation games, in enhancing

understanding and engagement. Many participants, both adults and students, reported a better understanding of wind energy concepts and a shift in their attitudes towards renewable energy initiatives.

The findings and positive reception of the workshops suggest that employing diverse collaborative methods increases the likelihood of engaging in renewable energy projects. Furthermore, such methods can play a crucial role in addressing misconceptions and building confidence. Policymakers are therefore advised to adopt a diverse set of methods – including early consultation, the use of VR simulations, and financial participation schemes – to strengthen local trust and enhance project acceptance.

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6 ANNEX

6.1 Annex I: Semi-structured interview conducted to assess the impact of project ramifications on respondent's concrete attitude towards wind energy projects

Table 5: Semi-structured interview

	Question	Answer
PART I General attitude towards wind energy	1_Do you believe climate change is human-induced and that it is one of the biggest problems of our times?	1 (strongly disagree) 2 (disagree) 3 (neutral) 4 (agree) 5 (strongly agree)
	2_ Regarding the environment do you agree that the protection of global biodiversity may require to accept worse conditions for local species?	
	3_Do you believe that our actions at the local level can make a difference to solving global problems?	
	4_Do you agree that everyone in your local society has a common responsibility to care for each other in challenging times?	
	5_When faced with a project challenge, do you prioritize finding the most effective solution regardless of cost?	
	6_When new technological innovations are introduced, do you think that debt should be taken on (with the associated risk) to explore and implement them?	
	7_Do feel that the problems relating to solving climate change issues are of too complex and that we lack the resources (time, training, etc.) to understand them?	
	8_Do you believe that radical changes, incl. technological advancements, (as opposed to traditional methods) are necessary to preserve our habitat and wellbeing?	

PART II Concrete attitude towards wind energy	9_How much do you know about Energy Transition in general?	1 (not informed at all) 2 (not well informed) 3 (moderately) 4 (well informed) 5 (very well informed)
	10_Do you feel well-informed about the (hypothetical) wind energy project in your region?	1 (not at all) 2 (slightly) 3 (moderately) 4 (well) 5 (very well)
	11_How do you feel about the (hypothetical) wind energy project in your region?	1 (very negative) 2 (negative) 3 (neutral) 4 (positive) 5 (very positive)
	12_How important do you see your participation in the wind project?	1 (not important at all) 2 (not important) 3 (neutral) 4 (important) 5 (very important)

PART III project ramifications	13_Which of the following technical changes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	A_change in setback distance	(i)
		B_technical measures to avoid bird strikes	
		C_change in turbine height	
		D_change in number of wind turbines	
	14_Which of the following financial participation mechanisms would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	A_discounted electricity / lower energy prices	(iii)
		B_possibility to acquire shares in the project with own money (dividends / appreciation of shares)	
C_possibility to acquire shares in the project with credit from project (dividends / appreciation of shares)			
	D_financial participation of the municipality		
	A_regular written information on the project progress	(iv)	

15_Which of the following options for engagement in the decision-making processes would increase your willingness to support wind energy projects in your region?	B_early involvement in the project planning and siting processes (once per month / quarterly)	
	C_involvement in the project implementation phase possibly also during construction (once per month / quarterly)	
	D_being granted elected representative of the municipality on the board of directors of the project (actual operation of wind park)	

6.2 Annex II: Guiding questions for interviews with workshop participants

1. **General perception** – What is your personal opinion on wind energy in general and its development in Europe?
2. **Local context** – How do you think wind energy could impact your community or region?
3. **Opportunities** – What benefits or opportunities do you see in the development of wind farms locally?
4. **Concerns** – Are there any aspects that worry you or that you think should be addressed more carefully (e.g. landscape, noise, biodiversity, tourism, health)?
5. **Social acceptance** – In your view, what factors could increase or decrease public acceptance of wind energy projects?
6. **Stakeholder involvement** – How do you think citizens and stakeholders should be involved in the decision-making processes?
7. **Support tools** – How useful do you find tools such as interactive maps or online forums to facilitate participation and understanding of projects?
8. **Fairness & benefits** – Do you think measures like financial compensation or community participation schemes could help build greater support?
9. **Personal experiences** – Have you had any direct or indirect experiences with wind projects? If yes, what worked well and what didn't?
10. **Future vision** – What role do you see for wind energy (and renewables in general) in the energy transition of your territory?

6.3 Annex III: Identified relevant stakeholders in the Ennstal, Styria

Table 6: Identified stakeholders for the pilot site in the Ennstal

Stakeholder	Geographical level
Politics	
Austrian Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management	National
Austrian Federal Ministry of Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology; Section VI - Climate and Energy	National
Federal state Styria, Department 13 Environment and Spatial Planning	Regional (Styria)
Federal state Styria, Department 17 Country and regional development, unit for State Planning and Regional Development	Regional (Styria)
RML Regionalmanagement Bezirk Liezen GmbH	Local
Municipality Aich	Local
Municipality Grundsee	Local
Municipality Gröbming	Local
Municipality Lassing	Local
Municipality Irdning-Donnersbachtal	Local
Municipality Rottenmann	Local
Municipality Admont	Local
Municipality Liezen	Local
Municipality Landl	Local
Environmental organisations	
Environmental advocacy office Styria	Regional (Styria)
Federal state Styria, Department 13 Environment and Spatial Planning, unit nature conservation	Regional (Styria)
Federal state Styria, Department 15 Energy, Housing, Technology, Climate Protection Coordination Unit	Regional (Styria)
Umweltdachverband	National
Styrian Nature Conservation Association	Regional (Styria)
Naturfreunde Liezen	Local
Birdlife Austria	National
Birdlife Austria – Styria regional office	Regional (Styria)
Österreichischer Alpenverein, Sektion Liezen	Local
Österreichischer Alpenverein, Abteilung Raumplanung und Naturschutz	National
Austrian Federal Forests	National
Steirischer Jagdschutzverein (Zweigstelle Liezen)	Regional
ÖKOBÜRO	National
Economy	
Styrian Economic Chamber – Industry sector	Regional (Styria)
Styrian Economic Chamber – Tourism and leisure sector	Regional (Styria)
Styrian Chamber of labour – Economic Policy Department	Regional (Styria)
Styrian Chamber of labour – Focus: Europe, spatial planning, climate	Regional (Styria)
Styrian Chamber of labour – Focus: Energy, environmental subsidies	Regional (Styria)
Styrian chamber of agriculture - committee on Energy, Climate and Bioresources	Regional (Styria)
District chamber of agriculture and forestry (Liezen)	Local

Styrian Trade Union Federation	Regional (Styria)
Erneuerbare Energie Österreich (EEÖ)	National
Österreichs Energie	National
IG Windkraft	National
Industry	
Energie Steiermark Green Power GmbH	Regional (Styria)
Wien Energie GmbH	National
ENERCON GmbH – Zweigniederlassung Österreich	International
GE Wind Energy GmbH	International
LEITWIND	International
Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy GmbH	International
Vensys Energy AG	International
Vestas Österreich GmbH	International
ECOWind Handels- und Wartungs GmbH	National
ENAIRGY Windenergie GmbH	Regional
Energiewerkstatt Verein – Technisches Büro	National
EWS Consulting GmbH – Efficient Wind Power Solutions	National
PROFES - Professional Energy Services GmbH	National
GeoSphere Austria	National
EVN Naturkraft	National
ImWind Erneuerbare Energie GmbH	National
Windheimat GmbH	Regional
ConPlusUltra GmbH	National
Ventus Engineering GmbH	International
Tourism	
Federal state Styria, Department 12 Economy, Tourism, Science and Research	Regional (Styria)
Liezen office Gesäuse Tourism Association	Regional
Steirische Tourismus und Standortmarketing GmbH- STG	Regional (Styria)

